

Village Drama Against Malaria

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Research Unit (Public Engagement with Research conference, University
of Oxford, July 2021)

- Collaboration between University of Oxford and Mahidol University, funded by Wellcome Trust
- > 40 years old
- Dedicated Bioethics & Engagement team, established in 2015 (though we have been engaging communities for many years)
- Why bioethics and engagement?
- Embedding public/community voices in research ensures that our research is responsive, impactful and ethical
- ~20 staff, core staff in Bangkok, Oxford, Mae Sot, Siem Pang, Siem Reap, Vientiane

- Bangkok hub, but conducting clinical research internationally
- Tropical medicine and infectious diseases
- E.g. Malaria, antimicrobial resistance, tuberculosis, maternal and child health, COVID-19

Village Drama Against Malaria

Cambodia, 2016-2019

Malaria in Cambodia

- We know that there is multidrug-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* in the Greater Mekong Subregion
- Threatens global malaria elimination efforts
- If resistance spreads to Africa...
- 2016 – we conducted a cluster randomized trial on mass antimalarial drug administration (MDA), subsequently other research
- Mass drug administration - for entire villages. Need high coverage.
- If participation ('coverage') is poor the efficacy is reduced substantially

Aim of Village Drama Against Malaria

- In order to understand the research, villagers need to understand malaria
- If you have fever, go to your village malaria worker immediately
- Sleep under bednet
- VDAM was created! – ran alongside other engagement efforts ran by local health authorities, NGOs and malaria researchers.

Children dressed up as mosquitoes

- This was a project in rural Cambodia where literacy is low
- We partnered with a local drama company and health authorities
- We created a draft script for a comedy sketch about malaria. Then together we went from village to village. In each village we work together with the village administration and school teachers.
- We spent 3 days in each village.

The drama group and our team travelled from village to village in the target provinces. Villages were chosen based on the reported malaria incidences in preceding years

In each village, the drama team conducted art, theatre and singing workshops for school children

And a crash course on dancing

In addition, together with their teachers, we taught children about malaria, and gathered local malaria-related stories and embedded them into a comedy sketch about malaria.

 សាលាបឋមសិក្សា ខ្លីណាង
UWS Kei Nang Primary School
www.unitedworldschools.org

ចូលរួមទាំងអស់គ្នា ប្តេជ្ញាលុបបំបាត់ ជម្ងឺគ្រុនចាញ់នៅឆ្នាំ២០២៥

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On the final evening, there was a big performance at the village square or temple.

Younger children sang songs about malaria, a handful of older children participated in the 45-minute comedy drama alongside professional performers. There were also malaria quizzes with prizes

A very exciting event for village children

Even more exciting for their parents and grandparents

Evaluation – multiple indicators

- Quantitative
 - Attendance
 - Recruitment to our mass drug administration study
- Qualitative
 - Interviews with participants, drama team, project partners, villagers
 - Held two workshop with stakeholders
- Others
 - Media coverage in Cambodia
 - Decrease in malaria cases
 - Publications
 - VC award

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The impact of targeted malaria elimination with mass drug administrations on falciparum malaria in Southeast Asia: A cluster randomised trial

Lorenz von Seidlein^{1,2*}, Thomas J. Peto^{1,2}, Jordi Landier^{3,4}, Thuy-Nhien Nguyen⁵,

THE LANCET

Log in

CORRESPONDENCE | VOLUME 388, ISSUE 10063, P2990, DECEMBER 17, 2016

Village Drama Against Malaria

Renly Lim • Thomas J Peto • Rupam Tripura • Phaik Yeong Cheah

Published: December 17, 2016 • DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)32519-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32519-3)

In total, VDAM reached 55 villages and 43502 attendees

Table 1. Number of villages, participants and audience members for the Village Drama Against Malaria project from 2016 to 2019.

Year	Province in Cambodia	Number of villages	Number of *participants	Number of audience members
2016	Battambang	20	300	8620
2017	Pailin	15	600	12,410
2018	Stung Treng	10	955	13,610
2019	Stung Treng	10	523	8842
Total		55	2378	43,502

*Young people involved in the performances (e.g dancing, comedy malaria-themed sketches, fashion show) and competitions

"For me, I really enjoyed the opportunity to participate here ... And they (the drama group) have helped us know about how to avoid malaria in order to raise general health ... We will remember this our whole lives! It is the first time for me to participate in this activity."
(14 year old girl, Battambang province)

“I told my family that they should sleep in a bednet and when they chat or drink beer, they should wear sleeved clothes.”
(drama performer, Stungtremg).

VillageDramaAgainstMalaria2016(7mins)

<https://youtu.be/vReFOm8V6OY>

Video by Nicky Almasy

Project team

Ean Mom, Nou Sanann, Dr Thomas Peto; Prof. Lorenz Von Seidlein;
Prof. Arjen Dondorp Dr James Callery; Dr Renly Lim, Dr Christopher
Pell; Dr Chea Nguon; Dr Rupam Tripura, Dr Yok Sovann, Chan
Davoeng, Ma Sareth, Pich Kunthea

Photo credit – Nicky Almasy and project team

Drama team from Pursat led by Mey Savon

Funding: Wellcome Trust

For more information

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MORU Engagement Strategy <https://zenodo.org/record/3510158#.YOF6DS8RpQJ>

Winner
**VC Public Engagement
with Research Awards**
2019
...and VC Choice Award

Thank you!
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